

The Influence of the Dielectric Constant of the Medium on the Rate of Coagulation of Arsenious Sulphide Sol by Electrolytes.

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It is well known that colloids are sensitised by non-electrolytes of low dielectric constant. The present position has been summed up by Freundlich ("Kapillar-chemie," 1922, 2nd Edition, pp. 636-639, also 358-359). Weiser in a recent paper (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 1253) points out that along with the effect of the dielectric constant the possibility that the non-electrolyte influences the coagulation by interfering with the adsorption of the active ions has to be taken into consideration. It would appear from the following quotation that Weiser got his clue from Freundlich :

"Hiermit ist die Mannigfaltigkeit des Einflusses der Nichtelektrolyte nicht erschöpft. Noch ehe die eben erörterte Sensibilisierung bekannt war, hatten Kruyt und van Duin auf eine eigentümliche Veränderung der Ko. W. beim As_2S_3 -Sol durch kapillaraktive Stoffe, wie Amylalkohol, Phenol u. a., hingewiesen. Sie beobachteten bei der Flockung durch einund dreiwertige Kationen eine Erniedrigung des Ko. W., also eine Sensibilisierung; bei zwei- und vierwertigen dagegen eine Erhöhung des Ko. W., also eine Beeinträchtigung der Flockung. Dies Verhalten lässt sich zurzeit schwer erklären. Es ist allerdings durchaus möglich, da die Flockung durch

Nichtelektrolyte beeinträchtigt wird: Sie können ja durch ihre Adsorption die Adsorption des aktiven Ions herabsetzen, weil sie es von der Grenzfläche verdrängen (siehe S. 278). Es würde dann eine grössere Konzentration, also ein höherer Ko. W. nötig sein, um die Flockung einzuleiten. Wie aber Verdrängung und Sensibilisierung ineinandergreifen, dass anscheinend ein besonderer Einfluss der Wertigkeit des Kations dabei zustande kommt, ist vorläufig nicht verständlich."

Weiser has studied the precipitation by electrolytes, of negative arsenious sulphide sol, and of hydrous ferric oxide and hydrous chromic oxide sols both in presence and absence of phenol and *isoamyl* alcohol. He explains his observations by developing Freundlich's suggestions in the following manner :

"(1) The adsorption of a non-electrolyte by the particles of a sol decreases the stability of the latter in the sense that less of the precipitating ions must be adsorbed in order to decrease the charge below the critical values necessary for agglomeration and precipitation. The extent of the sensitisation depends on the concentration and adsorbability of the non-electrolyte and its dielectric constant. This effect tends to lower the precipitation value of an electrolyte. The amount of lowering is greatest for electrolytes with weakly adsorbed precipitating ions that precipitates only in relatively high concentration."

"(2) The adsorption of a non-electrolyte by particles of a sol cuts down the adsorption of the precipitating ion of the electrolyte added to produce coagulation. This effect tends to raise the precipitation value of an electrolyte."

"(3) Since the factors mentioned above have opposite effect on the precipitation value of electrolytes, it follows that depending on the conditions, the precipitation value

may be increased, decreased or may remain unchanged, in presence of a non-electrolyte."

From the above we see that the influence of the non-electrolyte is ascribed to two factors: (a) its dielectric constant and (b) its adsorption on the surface of the colloid particles. The influence of dielectric constant is explained by Freundlich (*loc. cit.*), on the assumption that the lowering of the dielectric constant decreases *pari passu* the charge on the surface of the colloidal particle. He gives in support of this assumption some observations on ferric hydroxide sol. It is difficult to see how the charge can decrease with a diminution in the dielectric constant unless it is further assumed that substances of low dielectric constant have an effect on the adsorption of ions to which the origin of the charge on the surface is referred. Further both Freundlich and Weiser assume that a diminution of the charge in presence of a non-electrolyte indicates a diminution of stability on the part of the colloid. This assumption has been the basis of all theories on the coagulation of colloids by electrolytes since Hardy first pointed out the relationship between the charge and the stability. In a recent paper Mukherjee and Chaudhury (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1925, 2, 307) have measured the migration velocity of colloidal arsenious sulphide in presence of acetic, formic and oxalic acids and have found that the rate of migration does not determine the stability of the sol. Thus the sol is not coagulated by 10*N* acetic acid and it is coagulated by *N*-hydrochloric acid; acetic acid diminishes the charge to a much greater extent at the same hydrogen ion concentration than hydrochloric acid does. They point out that a diminution in the dielectric constant brings about two effects:

(1) The electrical work, resulting from the displacement of the ions constituting the mobile sheet of the

double layer and surrounding the colloidal particles when two particles approach sufficiently near each other, will increase with a diminution of the dielectric constant. The result will be that the percentage of the total number of collisions between particles that are successful in bringing the particles so close to each other as to allow the surface forces to act and to lead to a stable aggregation will rapidly diminish. This effect will tend to stabilise the sol.

From the theory of the "electrical" adsorption (advanced by one of us) of precipitating ions it follows that the adsorbability will increase in a medium of low dielectric constant. This will sensitise the sol. The net effect will depend on the relative magnitudes of the two opposing factors.

The following experiments were undertaken with a view to investigate the subject from this point of view. Moreover it was thought desirable to compare the results obtained in presence of an electrolyte with a low dielectric constant in the light of the theories advanced to explain the mechanism of coagulation with mixtures of electrolytes.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Colloidal solutions of arsenious sulphide were prepared according to the method described in previous papers with excess of arsenious sulphide which was removed by passing a stream of hydrogen. Coagulation experiments were done by noting the time of complete disappearance of a filament of light from the time of mixing. The current consumed in illuminating the filament was kept constant (see Mukerjee and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1924, 1, 213). Equicoagulating concentrations of hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid, potassium chloride, barium chloride

and aluminium chloride in presence of different amounts of methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, formic, acetic, propionic and oxalic acids were determined. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE I.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol--Ethyl Alcohol.

Percentage concentration of ethyl alcohol.	Electrolyte concentration in normality.					
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	KCl	LiCl	BaCl ₂	AlCl ₃
0	0.03800	0.04985	0.05944	0.07073	0.001911	0.0002184
2.5	0.03675	0.04985	0.06064	0.07291	0.001985	0.0002146
5	0.03525	0.04985	0.06301	0.07211	0.002058	0.0002146
10	0.03400	0.04985	0.07055	0.07437	0.002278	0.0002109
15	0.03300	0.04985	0.07847	0.08021	0.002572	0.0002109
25	0.03500	0.04985	0.00618	0.08750	0.002940	0.0002033

TABLE II.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol—Methyl Alcohol.

Percentage concentration of methyl alcohol.	Electrolytic concentration in normality.					
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	KCl	LiCl	BaCl ₂	AlCl ₃
0	0.04450	0.04927	0.06024	0.07394	0.001834	0.0001995
2.5	0.04325	0.04927	0.05909	0.07086	0.001771	0.0001957
5	0.04225	0.04927	0.05888	0.06932	0.001727	0.0001920
10	0.04050	0.04927	0.05707	0.06624	0.001624	0.0001882
15	0.03850	0.04927	0.05470	0.06310	0.001544	0.0001770
25	0.03550	0.04927	0.05070	0.06008	0.001286	0.0001581

TABLE III.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol—Acetic Acid.

Concentration of acetic acid in normality.	Electrolytic concentration in normality.					
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	KCl	LiCl	BaCl ₂	AlCl ₃
0	0·03500	0·04900	0·05350	0·05631	0·001764	0·0002560
0·001	0·03500	0·04900	0·05200	0·055260	0·001800	0·0002446
0·01	0·03500	0·04900	0·05313	0·05313	0·001837	0·0002400
0·1	0·03500	0·04900	0·04800	0·04995	0·001874	0·0002384
2	0·03500	0·04900	0·03800	0·04144	0·001950	0·0002334

TABLE IV.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol—Propionic Acid.

Concentration of Propionic acid in normality.	Electrolytic concentration in normality.					
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	KCl	LiCl	BaCl ₂	AlCl ₃
0	0·0300	0·0500	0·05000	0·05631	0·001654	0·0003727
0·001	0·0300	0·0500	0·04600	0·05526	0·001654	0·0003652
0·01	0·0300	0·0500	0·04500	0·05313	0·001690	0·0003576
0·1	0·0300	0·0500	0·04125	0·04995	0·001690	0·0003352
2·0	0·0300	0·0500	0·02875	0·04144	0·001846	0·0003011

TABLE V.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol—Oxalic Acid.

Concentration of Oxalic acid in normality.	Electrolytic concentration in normality.					
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	KCl	LiCl	BaCl ₂	AlCl ₃
0	0·08000	0·05000	0·04688	0·05630	0·001654	0·0003426
0·005	0·02850	0·04700	0·04188	0·05034	0·001690	0·0004179
0·01	0·0275 ¹⁾	0·04550	0·03938	0·04834	0·001728	0·0004122
0·025	0·02650	0·04300	0·03688	0·04410	0·001874	0·0003915
0·05	0·02575	0·04100	0·03250	0·04037	0·001911	0·0003764

TABLE VI.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol—Formic Acid.

Concentration of formic acid in normality.	Electrolytic concentration in normality.					
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	KCl	LiCl	BaCl ₂	AlCl ₃
0	0·03000	0·04875	0·04436	0·05237	0·001654	0·0003163
0·001	0·02975	0·04800	0·04250	0·05081	0·001654	0·0003087
0·01	0·02875	0·04725	0·04000	0·04776	0·001654	0·0002937
0·1	0·02500	0·04600	0·03625	0·04313	0·001654	0·0002636
2	0·02550	0·04250	0·02433	0·02850	0·001654	0·0002937

From the above tables we find that as a rule the coagulating concentration of aluminium chloride diminishes with increase in concentration of the added substance with the exception that in the case of oxalic acid there is at first a marked increase followed by a regular diminution. For barium chloride with one

exception (methyl alcohol) the concentration goes on increasing or remains unchanged when formic acid is the added substance. In the case of potassium and lithium chloride, for five of the added substances, the colloid appears to be sensitised excepting the case of ethyl alcohol which stabilises the colloid against coagulation by these electrolytes. It is rather peculiar that the coagulating concentration of sulphuric acid remains constant in four cases out of six. Hydrochloric acid also has a similar tendency though in a large number of cases including that of ethyl alcohol its coagulating concentration decreases.

Regarding the added substances we find that ethyl alcohol shows by far the larger number of instances of stabilisation against coagulation by electrolytes, *e.g.*, potassium chloride, lithium chloride, and barium chloride.

One notices from the foregoing that the behaviour of a coagulating ion cannot be predicted from its valency. The observation of Kruyt and Van Duin (*Koll. Zeit.* 1915, 17, 123) that arsenious sulphide sols are sensitised by amyl alcohol and phenol against coagulation by uni- and tri-valent cations while, against bi- and tetra-valent cations a stabilisation is observed, cannot therefore be held to indicate a relationship between the behaviour of a cation and its valency. The observation that, with one exception, the added substance stabilises the sol against aluminium chloride is of interest in view of the fact that Weiser has disbelieved a similar observation of Kruyt and Van Duin. In the case of arsenious sulphide sol Weiser (*loc. cit.*), while explaining the difference in behaviour between potassium and barium chloride, finds it difficult to account for Kruyt and Van Duin's observation that the sol is sensitised against aluminium chloride.

Both Kruyt and Duin's and our observations prove conclusively that the simple explanation of Weiser is

insufficient. Further the conclusion that Weiser has drawn as to the displacement of adsorption of barium ion by *isoamyl* alcohol from his observation that less of barium is adsorbed when the latter is present is open to question; for, the amount of electrical charge carried by the particles determines the amount of adsorption of precipitating ions (*cf.* Mukherjee, *Faraday Society Discussion on Colloids*, Oct. 1920) and if the addition of non-electrolyte diminishes the initial charge of the colloid as has been assumed by Freundlich and by Weiser then this diminution alone may account for the small adsorption.

In this connection we would draw attention to similar observations by Mukherjee and Sen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 461) regarding the influence of hydrogen sulphide on the coagulation of arsenious sulphide sols by electrolyte (*vide* also Freundlich: "Kapillarchemie," 1922, p. 63).

We are inclined to believe that in all these cases the suggestion of Ostwald and of Freundlich that the main effect of the added substance is to lower the dielectric constant of the medium remains valid. But it appears to us that no clear conception as to how the dielectric constant affects the stability of the sol exists at present. As stated in the introduction Mukherjee and Chaudhury have shown that the fundamental assumption that a diminution of charge always means a diminution in stability as measured by the coagulating concentration of the ion is wrong. A clear explanation of the results obtained by us or by Kruyt and van Duin is not possible till a comparison of electrical charges under these conditions has been carried out.

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Received, July 27, 1926.